

RESEARCH REPORT

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Authorship Guidelines

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TREPA

Threat Reduction for the
Environment, People, and Animals

TREPA PUBLICATION SERIES

This publication is one of a series of scholarly products resulting from investigations of human dimensions of global environmental change. The Threat Reduction for the Environment, People, and Animals studies risk at the intersection of human-wildlife conflicts and diseases of animals using a team science approach.

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INTRODUCTION

The goal of this document is to clarify authorship and data-sharing principles to guide our collective work to investigate reducing security risks from the intersectionality of wildlife trafficking and biosafety from zoonotic pathogens in Africa's Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area. This document should be considered a 'living' document that may be collectively amended, as necessary, via the same deliberative and transparent process as its initial acceptance.

We recognize that our interdisciplinary scholarship is strengthened by our collective insights, the synergies between methods, disciplines, and theories. Our motivation for this work expands beyond mere intellectual curiosity and reflects a commitment to the people and the landscapes affected by the illegal wildlife trade. Let's also not forget that we are also committed to being friends throughout this process!

We agree that the following norms should guide future publications, presentations, and proposals that utilize and build on our collective work funded by the Defense Threat Reduction Agency.

AUTHORSHIP

Authorship should include all who have contributed directly and substantively to the work. We broadly accept the concepts described in [Yale University's Guidance on Authorship in Scholarly or Scientific Publications](#), and the [PNAS collaborative authorship guidelines](#). Centrally, these guidelines expect that:

- Each author should have participated sufficiently in the work to take public responsibility for its content, although the level of responsibility may vary among co-authors
 - All collaborators share some degree of responsibility for any paper they coauthor.
 - Some coauthors have responsibility for the entire paper as an accurate, verifiable report of the research. These include coauthors who are accountable for the integrity of the data reported in the paper, carry out the analysis, write the manuscript, present major findings at conferences, or provide scientific leadership to junior colleagues.
 - Coauthors who make specific, limited contributions to a paper are responsible for their contributions but may have only limited responsibility for other results.
 - While not all coauthors may be familiar with all aspects of the research presented in their paper, all collaborators should have in place an appropriate process for reviewing the accuracy of the reported results.”
- All co-authors should have been directly involved in all three of the following:
 - Planning and contribution to some component (conception, design, conduct, analysis, or interpretation) of the work which led to the paper or interpreting at least a portion of the results;
 - Writing a draft of the article or revising it for intellectual content; and
 - Final approval of the version to be published. All authors should review and approve the manuscript before it is submitted for publication, at least as it pertains to their roles in the project.

We also accept the concept that “Some diversity exists across academic disciplines regarding acceptable standards for substantive contributions that would lead to attribution of authorship. This guidance is intended to allow for such variation to disciplinary best practices while ensuring authorship is not inappropriately assigned.”

COLLABORATIVE PROCESS

Given the nature of our work as “Team Science” we are committed to inclusivity in the research process including in publication and presentation of results. Therefore, we commit to a deliberate collaborative process in generating research outputs.

1. Starting the Process

Anyone wishing to lead a publication, paper presentation, proposal, or “thought piece” drawing on, or inspired by the work of TREPA team members, should:

- Alert the entire group to the potential product early on its development, usually before the full design of the work has been completed;
- Invite group members to indicate interest in participation and authorship in the specific effort or to decline;
- Solicit statements of potential contribution from those who express interest, and have a conversation with the developing team about how the potential contributions may – or may not – work together to produce the final product.
- Solicit timely feedback (in writing) on abstracts and drafts; and
- Afford all co-authors, prior to submission, the opportunity to verify the accuracy and interpretation of the paper.

This “open door” process recognizes the distinct contributions made by team members and should lead to higher-quality research contributions.

2. Timely Reviews

A draft of any possible abstract, manuscript, presentation, etc., will be submitted to all potential co-authors with adequate review guidance (what do you need) and time to provide

comments (2-4 weeks for manuscripts, 1-2 weeks for conference abstracts and presentations). After receiving a draft, co-authors will provide feedback and comments within the publication type-specific time span mentioned above or can decline to participate. The author will integrate these comments as appropriate and circulate a revised version for approval prior to submission. We also recognize that the quality of co-author review feedback differs from that of a reviewer – as a co-author, if you suggest a change be made, you should also suggest how to make the change.

3. Order to Authorship

Typically, the person starting the publication process will act as the first author of the work and will be expected to contribute the largest amount of effort to the research and writing processes. If the project evolves such that another team member makes the largest contribution, the initiating team member should consider relinquishing first authorship. Generally speaking, the order of authorship should follow the level of contribution made to the finished project. In the case of a subjective “tie” the order of co-authorship should recognize and prioritize junior colleagues. The lead author is responsible for discussing and making these final decisions with the co-authors.

4. External Collaborators

Given the size and breadth of the research being undertaken here, it would not be surprising if additional external collaborators may become involved in the process. However, proposals for any potential external collaborators must be discussed among all PIs prior to any official actions being taken. It is the responsibility of the external collaborator’s point of contact to initiate this group discussion.

5. Proposals

If proposals for additional funding are based on the results of the TREPA research effort, the lead author(s) or PIs should reach out to our wider team to encourage participation and to enrich the intellectual merit/methods/broader impacts of a proposal. In general, we envision

that people be afforded the opportunity to opt-out or opt-in to the development of a new research proposal with the lead author/PI specifying clear guidelines for individual efforts in support of these grant proposals. We also recognize that not all research proposals for funding are of the scale that could financially support the entire TREPA research team. In such a case, the proposals must recognize the significance of the TREPA research effort in acting as a foundation for future research.

6. Funding Sources

While there is no inherently 'right' or 'wrong' source of funding, we can hold different views on the costs/benefits of different forms of support. PIs should be sensitive to the politics of grantsmanship and its long-term implications for scholarship, particularly regarding funds associated with particular agendas. It is essential that all team members be able to weigh in and transparently debate the nature of the networks through which our collective ideas might circulate in the process of submitting proposals.

7. Field Data Collection

Anyone planning to work in an area in which another team member has built connections should work closely with that region's 'ethnography expert(s)' to ensure that their research efforts in no way put at risk research participants or ethnographers' relationship with those participants.

8. Data Curation and Management

Data collected or developed as part of this project will be made available to all team members, to the extent possible, to those who have made a significant contribution to our collective efforts. Otherwise, any primary data associated with the project are not to be shared with individuals outside our group without the consensus of the entire research group and acknowledgment by the party of these authorship guidelines. The constraints of the funding agency and the cognizant human or animal subjects review boards will guide the good practices of data sharing.